

Rapporti Tecnici INAF INAF Technical Reports

Number	179
Publication Year	2022
Acceptance in OA@INAF	2022-09-07T11:57:37Z
Title	BC-SIM-TN-003 - Reports and Note Layout and Flow - Version 2
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Handle	http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12386/32552 ; https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179

BC-SIM-TN-003

Reports and Note Layout and Flow

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Change Log

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description
2	0	05/09/2022	Section 3	Author list policy updated

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

In this document, we describe the name convention, the format, the flow of reports, notes, and plans produced for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM (SIMBIO-SYS). A template is attached to this document.

1.2 Reference Document

[RD1] SIM-BC-YY-XXX - Template of the report (attached).

1.3 Acronyms

ASW	Application SoftWare
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FOP	Flight Operation Plan.
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
PI	Principal Investigator
ME	Main Electronics
OA	Open Access
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PE	Proximity Electronics
PL	Planning Report
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TC	Telecommand
TM	Telemetry
TN	Technical Note
TR	Technical Report
UM	User Manual
VIHI	Visible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

2 Name Convention

The document names will be created using the following template: **BC-SIM-YY-XXX**.

YY is an alphabetical code for the document collection from the list below:

LI: Lists of sheets that collect relevant information,

MN: minutes of internal meetings,

PL: documents for the planned test, phase or campaign of observation,

TN: technical notes,

TR: technical report,

UM: user manual of software or tool that will be distributed to the team,

XXX is the progressive number of each collection. The author will contact the archive manager, Romolo Politi (romolo.politi@inaf.it), to obtain the first available progressive number.

3 Authors list

The definition of the list of authors is defined in coordination with the Instrument PI and Co-PIs. The authors are divided into two groups:

1. the first group is formed by the editors of the document whose name order reflect the entity of the respective contribution,
2. the second group contains first the PI and then all the Co-PIs (if not included in the first group) strictly in alphabetical order.

4 Approval Flow

The final version of the document will be sent to the approval flow. If the document is for a single SIMBIO-SYS channel it must be revised by the Co-PI of the channel and approved by the PI. If the document is relative to the instrument it must be approved by the PI and all the Co-PIs.

5 Test documents flow

For a test session, a specific document flow has been defined which is formed by:

1. **Test Planning**: it describes all the tests of the session. It focuses on:
 - describing the scope of the test;
 - the timing and the sequence of the test;
 - list of the PDOR and FOP used for the test.

The document will be archived in the PL collection.

2. **Simulator Report**: it describes the results of the simulator, in particular, the number of images for each session, the duration of each session, and the total data volume produced for each test. The document will be archived in the TR collection.
3. **EGSE Report**: it describes the data produced by each test. Specific sessions are dedicated to:
 - summary of the TM data;
 - check of produced images;
 - check of the HK parameters;
 - check of the packets lost;

- ME and PE negative events;
- TC rejected.

The document will be archived in the TR collection.

4. **Channel report:** it describes the results of the channel tests, opening issues if the channel has not nominal behavior or closing them if the previous, not nominal behavior is understood. It should contain the summary and the scopes of the TCs commanded during the tests.

The document will be archived in the TR collection.

5. **Instrument report:** it is a summary of the channel tests and describes the inter-channel ones. It refers to the more detailed analysis described in the single channel reports. It could be used as report for ESA.

The document will be archived in the TR collection.

6 Submission and repositories

The reports, in their final version, are archived in PDF version in the Documents folder located in the shared GDrive [SIMBIO-SYS](#).

The PLs, TNs, TRs, and UMs will be archived in the INAF Open Access repository (<https://openaccess.inaf.it>) and will be validated by an external referee.

The delivery to the OA Archive of any kind of software and related UM, e.g. ASW, reduction and calibration pipelines, analysis tools, etc., must be discussed case by case.

6.1 Submission guidelines

All the Planning, Technical Notes, Technical Reports must be submitted in **Section 4.01** of the Open Access Archive to obtain the Handle and the DOI. The DOI is necessary for the registration of the report in the ORCID site, e.g. Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of TR imported in ORCID.

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At the end of the review process, when the document is accepted and the associated DOI is delivered, the first author will add it to the ORCID website, using the procedure “Add DOI”, and will contact Cristina Re (cristina.re@inaf.it) for the update of the ESA webpage.

The use of Open Access section 4.01 for the submission could change based on the Open Access policy evolution.

7 Document Versioning

A new version of a delivered report will follow the standard delivery procedure. The version number must be added to the title, starting from version 2. The author can also add the delivery date to the file name.